

Synthesis of Azabicyclo[3.3.1]nonanes and Dibenzo[*b,d*]pyrans from 3-Aryl-2,4-dicarboethoxy-5-hydroxy-5-methylcyclohexanones as Potential Antimicrobial Agents[†]

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Double Mannich reaction of **1a, c** with formalin and benzylamine or cyclohexylamine gave 3-azabicyclo[3.3.1]nonane derivatives (**2a, b**), while the Pechmann reaction of **1a, c** gave the dibenzopyrans (**4, 5**). The structures of the compounds have been confirmed by ir, pmr and mass spectral data.

MANY derivatives of 3-azabicyclononanes possess biological activities¹. The analgesic activity has been determined for more than 26 derivatives. The citrate salt of some of the derivatives has an analgesic potency approximately 3 times greater than that of meperidine². Several substituted-azabicyclononanes are useful as sedatives, psycholeptic and hypoglycemic agents³. Quaternary salts of certain derivatives are found to exhibit neuromuscular blocking activity⁴. The evaluation of the biological activity of compounds incorporating certain structural features common to a number of CNS/CVS agents in a rigid framework prompted us to undertake the synthesis of diethyl-3-azabicyclo[3.3.1]nonane derivatives (**2a, b** and **3a, b**) and dibenzo[*b,d*]pyrans (**4, 5**).

In a previous work⁵ we reported the synthesis of 3-aryl-2,4-dicarboethoxy-5-hydroxy-5-methylcyclohexanones (**1a-d**) by reaction of ethyl acetoacetate with benzaldehyde, *p*-methylbenzaldehyde, *p*-anisaldehyde and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde. The 3-phenyl derivative (**1a**) has been reported by Lal and Bahaduri⁶.

In a study towards the synthesis of azabicyclononanes, the application of double Mannich reaction of **1a, c** has been investigated. Thus, treatment of **1a, c** with formaline and benzylamine in a molar ratio of (1 : 2 : 1) afforded diethyl 3-benzyl-6-hydroxy-6-methyl-9-oxo-8-aryl-3-azabicyclo[3.3.1]nonane-1,7-dicarboxylate, oxalate (1 : 1) salt (**2a, b**). These compounds show carbonyl absorption bands in their ir spectra at 1730–1735, 1690–1695 and 1675–1675 cm⁻¹ and one OH absorption band at 3430–3410 cm⁻¹. The peaks at 1690–1695 cm⁻¹ indicate that carbonyl group at position-7 was hydrogen bonded (*cis* to OH). The ¹H nmr spectra of (**2a, b**) displayed signals at δ 4.7–4.72 (d, *J* 11.5 Hz) assigned to the protons of C-2 and C-4 attached to N–CH₂C₆H₅. The signal for the other methylene protons appear at

δ 4.35–4.36. The peak observed at δ 2.14–2.18 is assigned to methyl protons at C-6. Compound **2a** gave no molecular ion, but the observed fragment *m/z* 461, corresponding to C₂₀H₂₁NO₅, was obviously formed by loss of oxalic acid and water from the parent ion. However, on the basis of the known behaviour for β -cleavage of amines⁷, the major fragmentations have been observed.

1a; Ar = C₆H₅
1b; Ar = C₆H₄CH₃-*p*
1c; Ar = C₆H₄OCH₃-*p*
1d; Ar = C₆H₄N(OH)₂-*p*

2a; Ar = C₆H₅
2b; Ar = C₆H₄OCH₃-*p*

A similar treatment of **1a, b** with cyclohexylamine gave diethyl 3-cyclohexyl-6-hydroxy-6-methyl-9-oxo-8-aryl-3-azabicyclo[3.3.1]nonane-1,7-dicarboxylate, oxalate (1 : 1) salt (**3a, b**). Confirmatory evidence for their structures is presented from the analytical and spectral data.

In the ¹H nmr spectra, complex signals appear at δ 2.3–4.5, comprising a H(8) methylene protons of the two CO₂CH₂CH₃, protons of the C-2 and C-4 and the methylene protons of the cyclohexane.

3a; Ar = C₆H₅
3b; Ar = C₆H₄OCH₃-*p*

Since chromonar⁸ shows activity as a coronary vasodilator, hence it prompted us to synthesise such

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dibenzopyrans via Pechmann reaction with **1a, b**. Therefore reaction of **1a** with *m*-cresol under the Pechmann conditions gave **6a, 7, 8, 10a**-tetrahydro-3,9-dimethyl-6-oxo-7-phenyl-6*H*-dibenzo[*b, d*]pyran-8-carboxylate (**4**). Compound **4** gave molecular ion M^+ at m/z 374 corresponding to $C_{24}H_{22}O_6$, which indicates the elimination of a molecule of water as inferred from the absence of OH absorption in its ir spectrum.

4 : $R^1 = H, R^2 = OH$
5 : $R^1 = OCH_3, R^2 = OH$

When **1b** was condensed with resorcinol in presence of polyphosphoric acid, the reaction gave ethyl **6a, 7, 8, 10a**-tetrahydro-3-hydroxy-9-methyl-6-oxo-7-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-6*H*-dibenzo[*b, d*]pyran-8-carboxylate (**5**). Confirmatory evidence for the structure of **5** is provided by the analytical and spectral data.

Experimental

Melting points (uncorrected) were determined on a Gallenkamp electric melting point apparatus. 1H nmr spectra were recorded on a Bruker 40 spectrometer, infrared spectra in chloroform, and mass spectra on a Varian Mat 711 direct inlet at 70 eV.

Diethyl-3-benzyl-6-hydroxy-6-methyl-9-oxo-8-aryl-3-azabicyclo[3.3.1]nonane-1,7-dicarboxylate, oxalate (1 : 1) salt (2a, b) : A mixture of **1a** or **1c** (0.01 mol), 37% formalin (0.021 mol) and benzylamine (0.01 mol) in dioxane (20 ml) was stirred for 20 h, and the ethereal solution of the product was then treated with ethereal oxalic acid to give the oxalate of **2a, b** (50%) : **Compound 2a**, semi-solid yellow compound (Found : C, 63.2 ; H, 5.91 ; N, 2.63. $C_{30}H_{25}NO_{10}$ (563.588) calcd. : C, 63.25 ; H, 6.19 ; N, 2.45%) ; ν_{max} (CHCl₃) 1730 (C=O ester), 1690 (C=O ester), 1675 (C=O) and 3430 cm^{-1} (OH) ; m/z (rel. int.) 461 [$M - C_6H_4O_2$] (0.5) (calcd. for $C_{28}H_{21}NO_8$), 388[461 - CO₂C₆H₅] (0.5), 315 [388 - CO₂C₆H₅] (0.5), 238 [315 - C₆H₅] (0.5), 134(26) and 91 [$C_6H_5CH_2$]⁺ (100) ; δ (CDCl₃) 4.70 (2H, H-2) 4.72 (2H, H-4), 4.35 (2H, CH₂-Ar), 2.14 (3H, CH₃) and 7.4-7.7 (10H, ArH) ; **Compound 2b** : semi-solid brownish material (Found : C, 62.49 ; H, 6.32 ; N, 2.44. $C_{31}H_{27}NO_{11}$ (599.618) calcd. : C, 62.07 ; H, 6.22 ; N, 2.33%) ; ν_{max} (CHCl₃) 1735 (C=O ester), 1695 (C=O ester), 1670 (C=O) and 3410 cm^{-1} (OH) ; δ (CDCl₃) 4.6 (2H, H-2), 4.65 (2H, H-4) and 4.21 (2H, CH₂-Ar).

Diethyl 3-cyclohexyl-6-hydroxy-6-methyl-9-oxo-8-aryl-3-azabicyclo[3.3.1]nonane-1,7-dicarboxylate, oxalate (1 : 1) salt (3a, b) : The compounds were synthesised as above from (**1a, c**) except that cyclohexylamine (0.01 mol) was used to give **3a, b** (40%) : **Compound 3a** : brown viscous oil (Found : C, 62.35 ; H, 6.72. $C_{29}H_{29}NO_{10}$ (560.598) calcd. : C, 62.12 ; H, 6.83%) ; ν_{max} (CHCl₃) 1725 (C=O ester), 1690 (C=O ester), 1680 (C=O) and 3450 cm^{-1} (OH) ; δ (CDCl₃) 2.3-4.5 (H-8, 2CH₂ of the two ester, H-2, H-4 and 5CH₂ of the cyclohexane) and 7.6-7.85 (5H, ArH) ; **Compound 3b** : yellow viscous oil (Found : C, 59.77 ; H, 6.85. $C_{30}H_{40}NO_{11}$ (590.628) calcd. : C, 61.00 ; H, 6.82%) ; ν_{max} (CHCl₃) 1720 (C=O ester), 1695 (C=O ester), 1685 (C=O) and 3435 cm^{-1} (OH) ; δ (CDCl₃) 2.35-4.45 (H-8, 2CH₂ of the two ester, H-2, H-4 and 5CH₂ of the cyclohexane), 3.72 (3H, s, OCH₃) and 7.45-7.75 (4H, ArH).

Ethyl 6a, 7, 8, 10a-tetrahydro-(3,9-dimethyl and 3-hydroxy-9-methyl)-6-oxo-(7-phenyl) and 7-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-6*H*-dibenzo[*b, d*]pyran-8-carboxylate (4, 5). **General procedure** : A mixture of (**1a** and *m*-cresol) or (**1b** and resorcinol) and polyphosphoric acid (molar ratio, 1 : 1 : 10) was heated at 90-120° for 1 h in an oil-bath. The reaction mixture was cooled, poured into ice-cold water, and the resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol to give **4** and **5** : **Compound 4** : deep-brown crystals (40%), m p. 185° (Found : C, 76.87 ; H, 6.31. $C_{24}H_{22}O_6$ (374.42) calcd. : C, 76.98 ; H, 5.92%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 1720 (lactone) and 1695 cm^{-1} (C=O ester) ; m/z (rel. int.) 374 [M^+] (3) (calcd. for $C_{24}H_{22}O_6$), 301 [$M - C_6H_5O_2$] (35), 257 [301 - CO₂] (2), 255 [257 - 2H] (1.5), 178 [255 - C₆H₅] (2), 88 [178 - C₇H₆] (3) and 82 (100) ; **Compound 5** : brownish crystals (55%), m p. 107° (Found : C, 71.35 ; H, 5.55. $C_{24}H_{22}O_6$ (406.42) calcd. : C, 70.92 ; H, 5.45%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 3450 (OH), 1715 (lactone) and 1685 cm^{-1} (C-O ester).

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